

Ether-linked pseudooligosaccharides : A brief overview of their synthesis and applications[†]

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Carbohydrates constitute one of the most important classes of compounds from the viewpoint of biological activity. Apart from their role in the sustenance of life or as structural ingredients in the biological domain, as in cell surfaces, or their involvement in numerous biological processes, two special carbohydrate molecules, D-ribose and D-deoxyribose, constitute the backbones of RNA and DNA, the essence of the living matter. The unit of carbohydrates is a monosaccharide such as glucose. Combination of two or more carbohydrate units via the expulsion of a water molecule (glycosylation) from the glycosidic OH of **1** and a non-glycosidic OH group of **2** leads to the formation of a disaccharide **3** (Scheme 1), and the repetition of the process results in the formation of oli-

gomer carbohydrates, which are expected to mimic carbohydrates in order to address many issues related to the biological role of carbohydrates. The class of compounds, which are close analogues of naturally occurring carbohydrates, are called 'pseudosaccharides'.

Pseudomonosaccharides may be represented by heterocyclic or carbocyclic rings containing contiguous OH groups. Examples of such systems are iminosugars, thiasugars and carbasugars. Two or more sugar units coupled via linkages other than glycoside linkage lead to what are known as pseudooligosaccharides. As an example, an ether-linked pseudodisaccharide such as **4** is also structurally derived by the expulsion of a molecule

Scheme 1. Formation of a disaccharide from monosaccharides.

gomer carbohydrates or polysaccharides. Biosynthetically the formation of these carbohydrate molecules is mediated by enzymes. These glycoside linkages are cleaved by enzymes called glycosidases. However, it is also neces-

sary to develop molecules, which are expected to mimic carbohydrates in order to address many issues related to the biological role of carbohydrates. The class of compounds, which are close analogues of naturally occurring carbohydrates, are called 'pseudosaccharides'. Pseudomonosaccharides may be represented by heterocyclic or carbocyclic rings containing contiguous OH groups. Examples of such systems are iminosugars, thiasugars and carbasugars. Two or more sugar units coupled via linkages other than glycoside linkage lead to what are known as pseudooligosaccharides. As an example, an ether-linked pseudodisaccharide such as **4** is also structurally derived by the expulsion of a molecule

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Scheme 2. Formation of an ether-linked pseudodisaccharide from monosaccharides.

different molecules of monosaccharides. An interesting feature of the ether-linked pseudooligosaccharides is that the anomeric positions of the monosaccharide units are free for further transformations.

As a matter of fact, little attention has been paid to this class of compounds, and only a handful of examples are available in the literature. This short review focusses on the synthesis of ether-linked pseudooligosaccharides reported previously by others and recently by the author. Some applications of these pseudosaccharides in the author's laboratory are also described herein.

In 1961, Whistler and Froein attempted unsuccessfully the derivatization of corn syrup with 5,6-anhydroglucose, and ended up with self-polymerization of corn amylose along with some degradation of the amy-

lose¹. However, they reported the formation of the 6,6'-ether-linked pseudodisaccharide **8** in 32% overall yield via the 1,2-isopropylidene protected pseudodisaccharide **7** by heating a melt of the glucose derivative **5** and 5,6-anhydroglucose **6** at 160 °C, followed by removal of the isopropylidene groups by treatment with aq. HOAc (Scheme 3)¹. The same authors also described the preparation of the glucose-galactose pseudodisaccharide **10** (Scheme 4)¹. Apart from the characterized sugar derivatives **8** and **10**, the aforementioned authors also described the formation of trace materials from the reaction of **5** and **6**, the structures of which were thought to be the 3,6'-pseudodisaccharide **11** and the 5,6'-pseudodisaccharide **12**, although no data were reported for them. The above work is probably the first recorded attempt to prepare an ether-linked pseudodisaccharide.

Scheme 3. Synthesis of 6,6'-ether-linked glucose-glucose pseudodisaccharide **8**.

Scheme 4. Formation of 6,6'-ether-linked glucose-galactose pseudodisaccharide **10**.

Later, ether-linked pseudodisaccharide structures appeared as side products in some instances of synthesis of

oligosaccharides. In a study directed toward the glycosylation of mannosyl derivatives, reaction of the stannyl protected mannose derivative **14** with the glucose triflate **16** afforded the desired disaccharide **17** (Scheme 5)². A side product **18** was also isolated in this reaction. NMR and mass spectral data indicated the 3,6'-ether-linked pseudodisaccharide structure for **18**. The formation of **18** was probably due to the involvement of

the stannyl derivative **15**, which resulted from the equilibration of **14** during the reaction and subsequently took part in the reaction. Similarly, reaction of the stannyl derivative of the benzylidene protected glucose **19** with the glucose triflate **16** gave rise to the 2,6'-ether-linked glucose-glucose pseudodisaccharide **20** along with the normal disaccharide **21** (Scheme 6).

In a study directed toward the synthesis of potential amphiphiles, Villa *et al.* prepared the 6,6'-ether-linked glucose-glucose pseudodisaccharides **24** in 66% yield by reacting the acetal protected glucose derivative **22** with the anhydro-3-*O*-alkyl-5,6-anhydroglucose derivative **23** in the presence of powdered KOH in 1 : 1 toluene-DMSO at 40 °C for 40 h (Scheme 7)³. Removal of the protecting groups by treatment with aqueous trifluoroacetic acid afforded the free pseudodisaccharide **25** as anomeric mixtures in 44% yield. The authors established that the glucose rings were present in the pyranose forms. Amphiphilic character of **25** was established, and the compound exhibited thermotropic and lyotropic liquid-crystalline properties.

In 1997, Pérez *et al.* reported the isolation of a carbohydrate from the root of *Acrocomia mexicana* and pro-

Scheme 5. Formation of 3,6'-ether-linked mannose-glucose pseudodisaccharide **18**.

Scheme 6. Formation of 2,6'-ether-linked glucose-glucose pseudodisaccharide **20**.

Scheme 7. Synthesis of an amphiphilic 6,6'-ether-linked glucose-glucose pseudodisaccharides **24** and **25**.

posed the 6,6'-ether-linked pseudodisaccharide structure **26** for the compound, which was named coyolosa⁴. Subsequently the authenticity of the structure, particularly the absolute configurations of the anomeric centers, was challenged by Ikegami *et al.*, who synthesized several 6,6'-ether-linked pseudodisaccharides having different monosaccharide units and came to the conclusion that coyolosa probably is an anomeric mixture of 6,6'-ether-linked mannose-mannose pseudodisaccharide **27**⁵. The most interesting aspect of the work was the development of a synthetic methodology for preparing ethers from an alcohol and an aldehyde via the acetals as shown in Scheme 8. An equimolar amount of a methyl glucopyranoside **B** reacted with an aldehyde **A** very slowly to give the acetal derivative **C** in poor yield. However, when an excess of **B** was used in the presence of trimethylsilyl trifluoromethanesulfonate (TMSOTf) at 0 °C, **C** was isolated in very good yield. Reduction of the acetal **C** by

Scheme 8. Acetalization of aldehydes **A** with alcohols **B** catalyzed by TMSOTf.

triethylsilane (TESH) then afforded the 6,6'-ether-linked pseudodisaccharide **E**, yields being generally in the range of 56–96% (Scheme 9). The biological activity (glucose tolerance in alloxane-induced diabetic rats) of several 6,6'-ether-linked pseudodisaccharides synthesized by the above methodology was determined and compared with that of coyolosa. The authors proposed on the basis of this structure-activity relationship (SAR) that the structure of coyolosa was probably **27**, the mannose-mannose pseudodisaccharide, which had similar activity as coyolosa.

The unusual structure of coyolosa led Haines to make investigations similar to that described above^{6,7}. He developed a convenient strategy for 6,6'-ether-linked pseudodisaccharides as shown in Scheme 10. The method

Scheme 9. TESH mediated reduction of acetal **C** to 6,6'-ether-linked pseudodisaccharide **E**.

is essentially based on a displacement reaction involving the triflate leaving group and is illustrated by the reaction of the allose derivative **28** and the allose triflate **29**, giving rise to the protected 6,6'-ether-linked pseudodisaccharide

Synthesis of 3,5'-ether-linked pseudooligosaccharides

As mentioned earlier, ether-linked pseudooligosaccharide derivatives have received little attention, and only a few 2,6'-, 3,6'- and 6,6'-ether-linked dihexoses described

Scheme 10. A new approach to 6,6'-ether-linked pseudodisaccharides by displacement of triflate.

30 in 91% yield. Complete deprotection of **30** afforded the pseudodisaccharide **31**. Several 6,6'-linked pseudodisaccharides were synthesized by this method. Comparison of the NMR spectral data of these compounds with those of coyolosa led to the conclusion that coyolosa may not be a 6,6'-ether-linked pseudodisaccharide at all. Possibly it is a 1,1'-linked disaccharide. It appears, therefore, that the structure of coyolosa still remains unresolved. However, coyolosa has rekindled interest in ether-linked pseudodisaccharides. As mentioned earlier, the presence of free anomeric hydroxyl groups offered a scope for derivatization at the anomeric centers, particularly by nucleobases leading to nucleosides. While thinking in this direction, we at IICB realized that 3,5'-ether-linked pseudooligopentoses with the generalized structure **32** (Fig. 1) would be important targets for synthesis, because DNA and RNA have ribose units linked via 3- and 5-oxygen atoms.

Fig. 1. Example of 3,5'-ether-linked pseudooligopentoses.

above are known. A 3,5'-ether-linked oligopentose molecule such as **32** is of particular interest due to the close similarity of the ether linkage to the nucleic acid backbone. This realization led us to undertake a program directed toward the synthesis of 3,5-ether-linked pseudooligosaccharides. Apart from using these novel sugar derivatives for the synthesis of RNA analogs, we also planned to employ them in our ongoing intramolecular carbohydrate nitrene and nitrile oxide cycloaddition

chemistry. With this end in view we reported in 2005 the synthesis of the first examples of 3,5'-ether-linked oligopentose derivatives from readily available carbohydrate precursors⁸. The synthetic strategy is illustrated by the preparation of the pseudodisaccharide **35** (Scheme 11). However, the seemingly easy task of making a 3,5'-ether linkage by coupling of two carbohydrate units appeared

heating a mixture of **33** and **34** in 11% aq. NaOH in the presence of tetrabutylammonium bromide at 70 °C for 70 h and the protected pseudodisaccharide **35** was obtained in 88% yield. A minor but expected side product was the olefin **36**. The alkylation procedure was subsequently followed in the synthesis of all the other protected 3,5'-ether-linked pseudooligosaccharides. Side prod-

Scheme 11. Synthesis of a 3,5-ether-linked pseudodisaccharide **35**.

problematic. Alkylation of commercially available 1,2 : 5,6-diisopropylidene-glucopyranose (**33**) with the mesyl derivative **34** in the presence of NaH in THF or DMF was unsuccessful as were several other attempts to achieve the desired ether linkage by direct alkylation. Finally adoption of a method used by Tam *et al.* turned out to be effective for the crucial alkylation⁹. The method involved

ucts similar to **36** were encountered in many of these syntheses. Several pseudosaccharides were synthesized by following the above strategy and are shown in Fig. 2.

One important point to note is that the linkage between the two furanose units in these compounds consists of two atoms (one oxygen and one carbon atoms), but in order to make these pseudosaccharides useful for deve-

Fig. 2. Two-atom tethered 3,5-ether-linked pseudooligosaccharides.

loping nucleosides as RNA analogs, the linkage was required to consist of four atoms, because in RNA the backbone consists of four atoms (two oxygen, one phosphorus and one carbon atom). This led us to develop methods for the synthesis of four-atom tethered 3,5'-ether-linked pseudooligosaccharides as outlined in Scheme 12¹⁰. The strategy used the same method for alkylation as that described for the synthesis of **35**, except the precursor pentose derivatives had higher number of carbon atoms, as shown in Scheme 12.

Nucleosides from pseudooligosaccharides

The aforementioned 1,2-isopropylidene protected pseudooligosaccharides were easily amenable to conversion to nucleosides via deprotection and Vorbrüggen transglycosylation with nucleobases. As an illustration, Scheme 13 outlines the conversion of the methyl capped pseudotrisaccharide **44** to an uracil trinucleoside **57**. Both **55** and the corresponding hexaacetate **56** represent a mixture of eight diastereomers due to the presence of two

Scheme 12. Synthesis of four-atom-tethered 3,5'-ether-linked pseudodisaccharide **52** and pseudotrisaccharide **54**.

Scheme 13. Conversion of **44** to uracil trinucleoside **57**.

anomers of each furanose unit. However, application of the Vorbrüggen transglycosylation procedure to **56** led to trinucleoside **57** as a single isomer with β -nucleobase configuration, which was a mechanistic consequence of the reaction. The structures of all the nucleosides, which were later synthesized by following the same procedure, were established by IR, NMR and high-resolution mass spectral analyses. Similarly the other methyl capped pseudotrisaccharides **39**, **40** and **42** were converted to the corresponding uracil and adenine oligonucleosides¹¹.

Although the nucleoside **57** has the same stereochemistry at C-3 as in RNA, the backbone has only two atoms. So in order to synthesize closer analogs of RNA, the pseudosaccharides **52** and **54**, which have four-atom ether linkage, were converted to uracil nucleosides **59** and **60**, respectively as outlined in Scheme 14¹⁰. Comparison of **60** with RNA shown in Fig. 3 indicates that the phosphodiester group in RNA is replaced by the $-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-$ moiety in the non-ionic analog **60**. To our knowledge, **59** and **60** were the first examples of non-ionic ether-backbone analogs of RNA. Future research in this area is expected to furnish longer nucleosides with some structural modifications, which could be incorporated in native RNA for studying their compatibility with the native molecules.

Scheme 14. Synthesis of the first examples of non-ionic ether-backbone analogs of RNA.

Fig. 3. Structural similarity of **60** with a RNA fragment.

Intramolecular nitrile oxide cycloaddition on pseudo-saccharide templates

In 1990 we reported the synthesis of chiral cyclic ethers by *O*-alkenyl carbohydrate nitrone cycloaddition¹². In due course the strategy included nitrile oxide cycloaddition, and chiral cyclic ethers, amines and recently sulfides of diverse ring size and skeletal structures were obtained by the cycloaddition methodology¹³. Carbohydrate derivatives used for this purpose were limited to monosaccha-

rides. Pseudosaccharides described in earlier sections appeared to us to be of particular interest as substrates for cycloaddition, which would give rise to novel oxygen macrocycles. Accordingly, nitrile oxides were generated from the pseudosaccharide derivatives, and their *in situ* cycloaddition was studied. A common strategy for the generation of nitrile oxide precursors as well as their intramolecular cycloaddition (INOC) using **38** as the nitrile oxide precursor is shown in Scheme 15. An interesting aspect of this scheme is that a common aldehyde **62** gave rise two precursors **63** and **64**. Cycloaddition of **63** and **64** led to the formation of the oxygen macrocycles **66** and **68**, respectively, the latter being the next higher homolog of the former. Other macrocycles of different ring sizes were synthesized by the application of the above strategy and are shown in Fig. 4. The macrocycle **73** was derived from **72** by the cleavage of the dihydroisoxazoline ring.

Some of these isopropylidene protected macrocycles were converted to nucleosides **74**, **75** and **76** by methods discussed earlier in this review (Fig. 5)¹⁴. One of these nucleosides, **74**, was found to bind to an adenine nucleoside and exhibit interesting aggregation property¹⁴.

Scheme 15. Nitrile oxide cycloaddition on pseudosaccharide template.

Fig. 4. Oxygen macrocycles synthesized from pseudosaccharides by INOC.

Fig. 5. Nucleosides derived from macrocycles 69, 70 and 72.

In conclusion, this short review narrated the work done in the author's laboratory on a class of carbohydrate derivatives, which till now have not been much explored. There is definite scope of the synthesis of novel chemical entities from these ether-linked pseudooligosaccharides, and even pseudosaccharides themselves without any protecting groups are expected to be a topic of importance from the standpoint of interesting biological properties.

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References

1. R. L. Whistler and A. Froein, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 3946.
2. G. Hodosi and P. Kovác, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1998, **308**, 63.
3. L. Vanbaelinghem, P. Godé, G. Goethals, P. Martin, G. Ronco and P. Villa, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1998, **311**, 89.
4. S. Pérez, G. R. M. Pérez, G. C. Pérez, G. M. A. Zavala and S. R. Vargas, *Pharm. Acta Helv.*, 1997, **72**, 105.
5. H. Takahashi, T. Fukuda, H. Mitsuzuka, R. Namme, H. Miyamoto, Y. Ohkura and S. Ikegami, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2003, **42**, 5069.
6. A. H. Haines, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 835.
7. A. H. Haines, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2004, **2**, 2352.
8. J. Sengupta, R. Mukhopadhyay, A. Bhattacharjya, M. M. Bhadbhade and G. V. Bhoekar, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2005, **70**, 8579.
9. G. K. Tranmer and W. Tam, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2001, **66**, 5113.
10. P. K. Jana, S. N. Das, S. B. Mandal and A. Bhattacharjya, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2011, **52**, 6610.

11. J. Sengupta and A. Bhattacharjya, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2008, **73**, 6860.
12. A. Bhattacharjya, P. Chattopadhyay, A. T. McPhail and D. R. McPhail, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1990, 1508. corrigendum, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1991, 136.
13. (a) A. Bhattacharjee, S. Datta, P. Chattopadhyay, N. Ghoshal, A. P. Kundu, A. Pal, R. Mukhopadhyay, S. Chowdhury, A. Bhattacharjya and A. Patra, *Tetrahedron*, 2003, **59**, 4623; (b) K. V. Gothelf and K. A. Jorgensen, *Chem. Rev.*, 1998, **98**, 863; (c) M. Frederickson, *Tetrahedron*, 1997, **53**, 403; (d) H. M. I. Osborn, N. Gemmill and L. M. Harwood, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 2002, 2419; (e) S. Mukherjee, S. B. Mandal and A. Bhattacharjya, *RSC Advances*, 2012, **2**, 8969.
14. J. Sengupta, R. Mukhopadhyay and A. Bhattacharjya, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2007, **72**, 4621.

